

Project Number:
GA 101017408

Project Acronym:
UNITE.H2020

Project title:

Planning the Future of Research & Innovation in the European University Alliance UNITE!

UNITE.2020 Agenda and action plan

Version 1.0 – 30.06.2022

Deliverable 2.2

Deliverable

Project Title	Planning the Future of Research & Innovation in the European University Alliance UNITE!
Project Acronym	UNITE.H2020
Grant Agreement Number	101017408
Project Call	H2020-IBA-SwafS-Support-1-2020
Funder	European Commission
Project starting date	1st January 2021
Duration	36 months
Work Package	WP2 – Common Research and Innovation Agenda
Deliverable	Deliverable 2.2 – UNITE.2020 Agenda and action plan
Deliverable leader	Politecnico di Torino (POLITO)
Deliverable type	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> R - Document, report <input type="checkbox"/> DEM - Demonstrator, pilot, prototype <input type="checkbox"/> DEC - Websites, patent fillings, videos, etc. <input type="checkbox"/> OTHER <input type="checkbox"/> ETHICS - Ethics requirement <input type="checkbox"/> ORDP – Open Research Data Pilot <input type="checkbox"/> DATA - data sets, microdata, etc.
Dissemination level	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PU - Public <input type="checkbox"/> CO - Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services) <input type="checkbox"/> EU-RES - Classified Information: RESTREINT UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC) <input type="checkbox"/> EU-CON - Classified Information: CONFIDENTIEL UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC) <input type="checkbox"/> EU-SEC - Classified Information: SECRET UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)
Deliverable due date	30 June 2022
Deliverable submission date	30 June 2022
Author(s) – Partner(s)	Gianmario Pellegrino, Valentina Romano, Giorgia Novajra (POLITO)
Document version and date	v1.0 - 30 June 2022
Keywords	R&I Agenda; R&I strategy; Action plan; R&I pilot actions.
Abstract	<p>The UNITE.H2020 2030 R&I Agenda and action plan are aimed at articulating a common strategy to establish tighter links among alliance members and facilitate synergistic actions based on a careful analysis of the document “Unite! Challenges and Convergences Roadmap” (D2.1). It aims at complementing the Unite! 2030 Agenda, focusing on the alliance R&I dimension. The Unite! R&I agenda sees its first practical implementation in an action plan, made of feasible pilot transformation actions consistent with the policy of each partner, relying on the open science principles and coordinated through the different WPs.</p>

History of changes

Version	Date	Author(s) – Partner(s)	Reviewer(s) – Partner(s)	Description
v0.0	12.04.2022	Gianmario Pellegrino, Valentina Romano, Giorgia Novajra (POLITO)	WP2 members and WP leaders	First draft
v0.1	20.04.2022		Valentina Romano (POLITO)	First revised version
v0.2	06.06.2022		Roberto Zanino (POLITO)	Second revised version
v0.3	13.06.2022		Gianmario Pellegrino (POLITO)	Third revised version
v1.0	30.06.2022		Gianmario Pellegrino (POLITO) / Management Office (POLITO)	Final version to be submitted to EC

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Introduction

The 2030 R&I Agenda and action plan developed by UNITE.H2020 are aimed at articulating a common strategy to establish tighter links among alliance members and facilitate synergistic actions based on a careful analysis of the document “Unite! Challenges and Convergences Roadmap” (deliverable#2.1)

UNITE.H2020 shares of course the mission, vision and values of Unite! The present R&I Agenda aims at complementing the Unite! 2030 Agenda, focusing on the alliance R&I dimension.

The UNITE! R&I agenda of aims at enabling tangible progress of the partner universities and the alliance as a whole in line with the European Commission’s priorities, such as the European Green Deal and the UN agenda 2030, as well as seamlessly integrated with the education agenda which is being developed in the complementary Unite! Erasmus+ project, from which the European University Alliance UNITE! was born.

The UNITE! R&I agenda sees its first practical implementation in an action plan, made of feasible pilot transformation actions consistent with the policy of each partner, relying on the open science principles and coordinated through the different WPs. The pilots of UNITE.H2020 are the first seeds of the action plan, which oversees the longer time horizon of 2030. The action plan will have a measurable impact that will be approved by the partners’ leadership during the project.

Unite! Strategy

Reference is made to the Unite! European alliance as the framework of the UNITE.H2020 strategy, R&I agenda and action plan. The R&I agenda and the related Action Plan and Pilots are in line with the Unite! strategy, which is briefly summarized here. The Pilots will be the initial practical test-bed of the R&I dimension of Unite!, in line with the shared, integrated, long-term joint strategy on education developed in Unite! E+.

Identity

The European University Alliance Unite! aims to be

- A **model for a European University of innovation, technology and engineering**, assuming the leadership among universities to address the Sustainable Development Goals through the twin digital and green transition
- A **strategic alliance of universities** that is based on shared values, with a common vision and mutual trust, agile and dynamic, committed to sustained long-term collaboration and progressive integration
- A **bustling and inclusive community** of students at all levels, academics and staff, including the regions and partners of the member universities, with a strong sense of belonging
- A **trans-European meeting place of academic cultures**, spanning across Europe and having a global reach, imbuing its member universities with a rich diversity

Unite! stands out

- as a strong driving force for **technology and innovation** advancing a green and digital Europe
- for **transformative transdisciplinarity** that draws from engineering, science and the full range of multidisciplinary of the member universities
- for **distinctive focus areas** Unite! will strengthen its leadership in its established focus areas Sustainable Energy, Artificial Intelligence, Industry 4.0, Entrepreneurship. It will define new areas for which the alliance can achieve high visibility

Vision and Values

Unite's ambition is to

- realise **excellence in education, research and innovation** by creating unique new opportunities for students, academics, staff and further ecosystem partners.
- create and disseminate, jointly with the other European University alliances and with stakeholder organisations, pioneering innovations for the **European Education and Research Areas**.
- actively contribute to **European citizenship**, as well as to European attractiveness, resilience and competitiveness on a global scale.

Unite! is committed to

- the **European core values** of academic freedom, human dignity, liberal democracy, the rule of law, and social inclusion, as key constituents of the European way of life
- **ethical, safe and sustainable** technology and innovation, tackling climate change and its impacts, serving society, in line with fair and open science
- **diversity, inclusion, equity**, and the well-being of students and staff.

Mission

Unite!

- pursues a **forward-looking strategy**, focusing on high-quality, high-impact activities that become systemic and structural
- is **agile** in identifying and seizing new opportunities, in reacting promptly to impeding disruptions and in directing priorities and funds accordingly
- is **key to the member universities' strategies**, combining top-level commitment with broadly shared dedication
- implements **good governance** of the alliance and ensures accountable leadership, broad participation and supportive conditions for bottom-up initiatives.

Unite! Creates

- the hybrid (virtual, physical and blended) and multilingual Unite! trans-European Campus with easily accessible joint educational offerings, shared and pooled resources, efficient services and green mobility
- state-of-the-art learning opportunities with innovative pedagogies for challenge-based approaches, student-centred learning, and high-quality interaction in digital, hybrid and face-to-face learning environments
- a platform for the open exchange and the free circulation of talents and ideas, strengthening key skills and competencies, supporting diverse research and professional careers based on reformed research assessment, and offering unique opportunities for contributions
- a community that engages students as equal partners, enables staff to collaborate and participate in professional development all across Europe, and integrates citizens, entrepreneurs, start-ups and innovators into co-creation, knowledge exchange and joint actions within the alliance

Unite! Research & Innovation Dimension

The R&I dimension of the UNITE! Agenda is being developed by the UNITE! partners on the basis of the “R&I challenges and convergences Roadmap” developed within the UNITE.H2020 project in 2021 and according to the mission statement of the Unite! European University Alliance.

The R&I Roadmap identified commonalities among the partner universities in their strategic approach and aligned them with the European Commission, Member States and Regional research agendas, thus helping their respective research staff to tackle with the grand challenges of humankind.

The R&I dimension of Unite! takes also into consideration the Pact for Research and Innovation in Europe 2022¹ that will create an ERA fit for the future and mobilize research and innovation policies with concrete actions towards the challenges of today and notably the green and digital transitions.

As research universities, all the members of the alliance consider **research** together with **technology transfer and innovation**, as two important missions of their activity. Actually, all members of the consortium show an important contribution to the research activities in Europe according to the number and impact of their publications, **research projects funded in competitive calls and technology transfer activity together with innovation activities** like participation in the European Institute of Technology or creation of spin-offs.

The analysis of the strategic plans of the member universities regarding their approach to deal with R&I activities suggests similar patterns. All member universities include in their strategic plans a series of actions devoted to facilitate these activities, enhancing a culture of excellence including ethical attitudes, quality procedures operating in an **open environment**. Moreover, research activities at all universities depend to a large extent, but at varying degrees, on external competitive funding. Consequently, all universities align their strategies with the priorities of the funding agencies.

The commonalities found in this analysis provide the ground to establish a solid starting point of shared interests and goals, offering the opportunity for a substantial leap forward to the partner universities. A common theme that all partners include in their strategic planning regards actions to **attract talent** to their institutions. Ph.D. programs are commonly viewed as a key instrument to attract talent, so the members have put in place strategies to increase the number and quality of Ph.D. candidates. Similarly, increasing the number of postdoc positions is viewed by some universities as a strategic approach to attract talent. In regard to the attraction of mid-career researchers, member universities have different strategies, also in consideration of local regulations and relative restrictions.

Enhancement of **multidisciplinary research** is also a topic of common interest. All members assume that breaking the silos of traditional disciplines is key to perform innovative research activity and to be better positioned to deal with the great societal challenges. Of particular interest is to understand the institutional contribution to **deal with the UN SDGs**. For this purpose, member universities enhance multidisciplinary research through different organizational approaches like transversal platforms or research institutes that put together researchers of different fields to team up and boost the opportunities of innovation. This also permits to be aligned with the policies and strategies of the funding agencies, that incentivize the multi-disciplinary approach to innovation. A common strategy of the members is the investment on professional research services to support strategic research initiatives and to support researchers with proposal development and scanning for competitive research calls and opportunities.

Member universities include in their strategic plans the enhancement of a fair play atmosphere in the knowledge creation process. Specifically, an ethical approach to undertake R&I activities in the

¹ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *A pact for research and innovation in Europe*, 2022, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/56361>

framework of **open science** so that the outcome of the research is shared and easily reproducible by other researchers. Sharing raw data is also important since it opens the possibility to extract knowledge initially disregarded.

Member universities exhibit also a common interest in **servng society**, not only addressing great societal challenges, but **making the research activities reach the society**. Also in this line, members are important stakeholders in the respective regional developments both through talent attraction and through technology transfer and digitalization.

Another commonality found in the analysis of the strategic plans is the enhancement of an **entrepreneurial atmosphere in teaching and learning, as well as of the R&D activities**. Member universities devote important structural resources to chaperon entrepreneurs to develop their ideas and participate in the creation of spin-offs.

The analysis suggests that member universities share common strategies to deal with the goal of excellence in research, as well as technology transfer and innovation activities. The European University Initiative opens indeed new opportunities and related challenges. Working together permits sharing infrastructures, good practices as well as enhancing mobility and in general, being better organized to deal with the great societal challenges. In addition, the Alliance provides an opportunity to have more visibility and impact. The Alliance permits to show a unified voice within the diversity at the European level, representing a structure that aims at a European and global impact without losing its local impact. Finally, the alliance represents the opportunity to be better aligned with the policies of the European Commission and become an agile and efficient ally.

According to the 20 concrete actions identified in the new ERA Policy Agenda for 2022-2024 and in particular Action 13 “Empower higher education institutions to develop in line with the ERA, and in synergy with EEA”, the Unite! Alliance sets out 6 Research and Innovation objectives, listed below:

RESEARCH

- Objective R1: Enhancement of multidisciplinary research
- Objective R2: Promotion of a culture of excellence
- Objective R3: Research for society
- Objective R4: Open Science for knowledge co-creation

TECHNOLOGY TRANFER AND INNOVATION

- Objective I1: Enhancement of an entrepreneurial culture
- Objective I2: Digital transformation

These objectives drive the Unite! Research and Innovation Agenda and Action Plan, thus laying the basis for the Unite! European University towards 2030 and contributing to the priority areas defined in the Pact for Research and Innovation

Unite! R&I Agenda

The long-term vision of each partner converges into the common R&I Agenda of the Alliance, where the partners' strengths can complement each other towards a "whole beyond its parts", with the emphasis on the role of digitalization in this process even increased since the onset of the COVID-19 pandemics. The common R&I agenda will be translated into feasible transformation actions (action plan made of pilots/case studies), coherent with the policy of each partner and the open science principles. The agenda will help setting the basis for common policies for boosting R&I for a sustainable development. The topics in the Agenda reflect the work-package activities and pursue the above-mentioned R&I objectives.

RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES (WP3)

State of the Art

From the results of the first collection of Research Infrastructures of each partners, several possible synergies have been identified. Beyond the research topics included in the common focus of Unite! (Energy, Industry 4.0, Artificial Intelligence); also Environment and Health engineering have emerged as common topics of interest. The short term ambition here is to initiate working groups to share good practices and define common rules to open the Research Infrastructures to all Unite! members (booking, safety, remote access or preparation, cost and IP management,...). This will be illustrated in two pilot projects on electrical energy and living labs with application to smart districts. The long term objective will be to define a coherent vision of Research Infrastructure development considering the full Unite! ecosystem, avoiding unnecessary duplication of equipment.

Towards a Unite!2030 strategy for Research Infrastructures

The aim of UNITE! H2020 activities in this field is to share infrastructures and resources among partner institutions. First of all, each partner identified a relevant list of Research Infrastructures (RI) together with a Unite! classification. Not all RIs affiliated to the partner institutions are included in the related report (D3.1) in order to focus on UNITE! strategic domains. A benchmarking process has been put forward, with a selection of the best practices of the different institutions. In the future, further infrastructures may be added, or some of those already present may be removed, depending on the evolving partners' strategy.

An RI may apply to several research fields (we selected up to three), and a list of keywords should also be added to each in the future, in order to facilitate the searching of equipment and/or services among the partners' infrastructures. The list of equipment for each RI is not all-inclusive, but rather concerns important or outstanding equipment. The first deliverable comprises 103 research infrastructures. Each RI is described using a simple template, with a short description of the purpose and equipment (and/or services), including the possible Technical Staff for managing the RI, and a possible existing booking system to host external users, or an established remote access policy.

The access policy for internal users and for external users describes: the mode(s) of-and process(es) needed for- accessing , other conditions and restrictions, , the cost calculation method (unit costs/access costs...) and all other available information and support. The RI access policy must comply with the principle of non-discrimination. Other key information is the equipment available for remote access, the safety instructions and regulations, the regulation of intellectual property rights (IPR), the regulation of privacy (GDPR), and the open access/open data rules.

An amazing synergy between research topics (each RI has a "twin" somewhere else) has been found. Differences of RI development and organization have also been pointed out. A significant impact is expected from the sharing of good practices.

A joint list of doctoral students/researchers working in the areas of research of the RIs has been identified, which would benefit from shared infrastructures across the alliance. The rewards of involvement in Unite! should be obvious, including access to more RIs and therefore prospects of more recognition and/or more funding than with individual actions of the partners.

Two pilot research projects are planned in the field of

- (1) Electrical energy (PP1), and
- (2) Smart districts & living labs (PP2).

They have been selected for being of central interest to all the members of the Alliance, and also because they represent the different paradigms of sharing hardware (PP1) and sharing data (PP2).

CULTURE OF EXCELLENCE: HUMAN CAPITAL (WP5)

State of the Art

The partner universities are similar in terms of size and composition of research staff. The research staff was defined according to the HR Strategy 4 Researchers (HRS4R) process, that considers all persons carrying out research activities (including fellowship holders, bursary holders, PhD. students either full-time or part-time). Regarding HR management and, in particular, career development, gender and diversity, talent promotion, rewarding merit, all these aspects are very well addressed by the Universities but not all at the same level. For example, Gender Equality is well structured and monitored and all universities have dedicated units and/or institutional representatives, but other aspects such as .. A state of the art analysis on the best practices and approaches for the assessment of the academic merit has been developed. Also a benchmark analysis was conducted concerning current practices and regulations in the countries and universities that have an impact on possible common assessment. This second point includes some concerns that motivate our willingness to study a new framework. Finally, a gap analysis and a collection of best practices was carried out to identify common frameworks and common roadmaps.

Towards a Unite!2030 strategy for Human Capital

The consultations and discussions resulting from the WP5 Workshop allowed to identify relevant themes, which are common to all Universities, and to understand where their attention is being focussed nowadays:

- Attraction of researchers

- Internationalization
- Recognition of research work and equal opportunities in career progression
- Career development and mentoring of early career researchers
- Gender Equality and balanced work life.

A consultation made with the researchers, in the first phase of the project, allowed to identify gaps and needs. From the analysis of the results and discussions from the joint workshops the partners agreed that actions that would benefit from joint implementation are:

1. Tools to map the needs of Early Career Researchers (ECRs)
2. Training of Trainers in Mentorship
3. Universities can open the participation to some of their on-line training courses to the ECRs of partners
4. Supporting the mobility of ECRs by strengthening support for participation in Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions
5. Supporting the participation of ECRs in the call for proposals of the European Research Council (ERC)

Based on the researchers needs that were identified after a consultation, it was decided to develop further actions that they consider relevant to strengthen their careers. These are related to mentorship programs, oriented to early career researchers and actions to support the participation of ECRs in high impact grants. For that, a joint workshop will shade light on the best examples from partners and that will allow:

1. Partners to share/open their training/shaping researcher career actions, exploring joint tools as well as common practices.
2. By exploring and sharing existing mentoring strategies and activities to reinforce and up-skill research and research support staff, a common training approach is under development.
3. To enable researchers career development through mobility, partners will develop instruments to enhance mobility and research potential across UNITE!. These include for example, to raise the number of researchers involved in Marie Skłodowska-Curie actions and in the Visiting Research Fellowships scheme promoted by the ERC. While the first strengthens mobility and talent circulation across different partners, the second promotes exciting experiences in ongoing ERC projects to develop researchers' potential before they apply for their own ERC grants.

RESEARCH FOR SOCIETY: SOCIETAL OUTREACH (WP7)

State of the art

The analysis of some representative examples of outreach initiatives in place selected by each Unite! partner (focused on the research areas of UNITE.H2020 i.e. Energy, Artificial Intelligence and Industry 4.0, along with Sustainability, as transversal area of utmost importance for society) highlighted that among Unite! universities there is a very high number and variety of outreach activities, involving a very high number and variety of stakeholders, addressing a significant variety of SDGs, and mixing many different channels.

Many similarities and complementarities among Unite! partners exist in the outreach strategies in place referred to some key concepts:

- **Management:** The university members of Unite! do not focus on a single top-down or bottom-up approach but try to take advantage of centralized and decentralized strategies and to create virtuous circles that promote internal cohesion in the university's bodies and openness to society
- **Strategy and implementation:** outreach activities are strategic for all the partner universities; the activities analysed point to strategic documents that explicitly refer to outreach activities or pinpoint actual disseminated practices throughout the institutions
- **Actions:** All universities participate in networks of global, national, regional, and local range; depending on ongoing projects, outreach actions may focus on specific targets during specific timeframes.
- **Stakeholders and target:** Several different types of stakeholders are involved in the selected representative examples of outreach initiatives (e.g. industry actors or municipalities).
- **Objectives:** All universities have clear objectives for outreach activities. Some of these objectives are commonly mentioned (e.g., responsibility) and some are stressed by specific institutions, although implicitly shared by the others (e.g., democratic participation).

Considering the overall group of representative examples of outreach initiatives selected by all the partners, they cover all the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) adopted by the United Nations in 2015.

The following SDGs are address by all universities: 4_Quality Education, 7_Affordable and clean energy, 11_Sustainable cities and communities, 12_Responsible consumption and production, 13_Climate action, 17_Partnerships for the goals.

From the analysis of the state of the art in the different Unite! partner, a group of key-stakeholders was selected, which will be further engaged in future activities of the alliance. These stakeholders were individually interviewed to get input and give their perspective on societal outreach of universities, on the relation between their institution and the university as well as the SDGs as a framework for joint collaboration. The interviewed stakeholders consist of NGOs, public administrations, municipalities, foundations, professional associations, enterprises, innovation hubs, museums and non-profit organizations. The information depicted from the interviews shows that more than 90% of the stakeholders consider the SDGs framework as relevant and value adding for their institution. Moreover, the SDGs identified as being the most important for the objectives of the interviewed stakeholders were: SDG_3_Good Health and Well Being, SDG_4_Quality Education, SDG_5_Gender Equality, SDG_9_Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure and SDG_12_ Responsible consumption and production. The input from the stakeholders of the different partners about the role of universities, about their relation with the universities and about SDGs as a framework for their work, complements all the information collected and also helps in doing some comparison across institutions.

Towards a Unite! strategy for societal outreach and involvement of citizens in R&I

The selected group of key-stakeholders will be considered for their engagement in future outreach activities. The input from the interviewed stakeholders will be used as the basis for the identification of societal needs, the relation between the stakeholder and the university as well as the SDGs as a framework for joint collaboration. Any strategy for societal outreach developed within Unite! must

account for a great diversity of approaches and for the interaction of each partner with their local environments.

OPEN SCIENCE FOR KNOWLEDGE CO-CREATION (WP6)

The ultimate aim of open science should be the informed and extended co-creation of knowledge by all humanity. The goal of Unite is to progress towards this aim, by defining a set of objectives and providing recommendations for promoting, developing and implementing university and school level actions, redesigns and incentives for advancing the adoption of open science practices, principles and goals across the universities of the Unite! Alliance: Objective R4 - Open science for knowledge co-creation. These objectives and recommendations can guide, enhance and foster an open science culture and environment by boosting transparency, accessibility, legitimacy and participation in science among the Unite! research communities of researchers, students, staff, faculty, citizens and other professional groups in science.

The adoption of open science practices, principles and goals among the Unite! research communities can improve the quality both internal – academic– and external –societal– processes of learning and creation of new knowledge, increasing trust in science, nurturing innovative and entrepreneurial people, and accelerating research and innovation process for finding solutions for the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals established by the United Nations.

State of the Art

Open science is transparent and accessible knowledge, shared and developed through collaborative networks. It involves sharing ideas, data, methods and results with local, national, regional and global collaborative networks of research participants. It also goes beyond this to encompass scientific knowledge produced and used by these collaborative networks.

Science is being reshaped by advances in digital technology and tools, including big data, artificial intelligence, the Internet of Things, 3D printing and quantum computing, along with open digital and physical infrastructures, including open labs, open libraries, cultural heritage, digital knowledge bases and open university campuses. These technologies and infrastructures have, in turn, allowed researchers to experiment with, develop and adopt new open science practices, principles and goals for tackling grand societal challenges.

Open innovation is the use of purposive inflows and outflows of knowledge to accelerate internal and external innovation. Open science practices for the sharing of knowledge –open data, open access publishing, open protocols, open prototypes– and open science practices for the production of knowledge –transdisciplinary research, participatory design, citizen science, open collaborative tools– have created extraordinary possibilities to this knowledge value creation and transfer process. These practices are expanding not only the “ethos” in science, but also the “ethos” in innovation in universities. Open science practices are transforming science and innovation practices in universities.

Toward a Unite! strategy for open science

To support the development of a Unite! strategy for open science, we suggest five building blocks that best help constitute Unite! Alliance as a European engine of open science and innovation by 2023. The objectives and recommendations embrace the international framework for policy and practice set up by the UNESCO Recommendation on how to boost Open Science, approved on 23th November 2021.

Objective 1. Developing open science policies and open science strategies

Recommendation 1. Unite! Universities should develop or align their open science policies at university level, building on the UNESCO Recommendation on open science and their regional, national and EU policies, to boost a culture of openness across their research communities. These open science policies should define a common set of principles, standards, goals, career evaluation system, incentives and funding for the operationalization of open science at university level.

Recommendation 2. Unite! Universities should promote open science strategies at school level to implement their open science policies. These open science strategies should provide hands-on guidance on how to adopt open sharing and open collaborative science practices, and how to use open digital and physical infrastructures, taking into account the diversity of each research area.

Objective 2. Enhancing the opening up of digital and physical infrastructures

Recommendation 3. Unite! Universities should invest in university level digital infrastructures for the sharing and production of knowledge among their research communities. This university level digital infrastructure should ensure open as possible –ethical and legal– and permanent open scientific knowledge access – data, code, methods, prototypes, results – for everyone. This infrastructure should allow interoperability, guarantee implementing FAIR data principles, and ensure safety and security.

Recommendation 4. Unite! Universities should open their school level physical infrastructures for research, teaching and innovating, for everyone. They should create guidelines about the infrastructures access policies, training requirements and operation the tools and instruments.

Objective 3. Promoting open science support services

Recommendation 5. Unite! Universities should develop university level open science units for supporting their researcher communities along the different stages of the open scientific process. These units should provide seed funding and training in infrastructure, tools and skills that support and incentivise the adoption of open science practices, principles and goals among their research communities.

Recommendation 6. Unite! Universities should promote open science specialists at school level. These specialists should provide technical assistance, with regard to the specificities of each discipline of knowledge, and promote cross-border multi-stakeholder co-creation of knowledge among their research communities.

Objective 4. Fostering open science in careers

Recommendation 7. Unite! Universities should advocate the review of their regional and national research career evaluation systems to align them with the adoption of open science principles, practices and goals. These new career evaluation systems should give recognition to researchers for the co-creation of knowledge among collaborative networks of research participants.

Recommendation 8. Unite! Universities should adopt school level incentives for rewarding research processes and outputs related to the adoption of open science principles, practices and goals.

Objective 5. Improving open science competencies

Recommendation 9. Unite! Universities should promote multilingual open educational resources on open science for the capacity- building of their research communities. These resources should boost the participation in science among their research communities, composed of researchers, students, staff, faculty, citizens and partners.

Recommendation 10. Unite! Universities should open their training in open science infrastructure, tools and skills for everyone. Programmes, courses, MOOCs, workshops, seminars on-demand on open science should be promoted across their research communities and worldwide as a foundation stone of a European open science and innovation university.

ENTREPRENEURIAL CULTURE: ACADEMIA-INDUSTRY COOPERATION (WP4)

The definition of the value proposition for the Unite! alliance aims at define the added value of Unite! for industry, compared with the current value proposition of the partner Universities. Strictly connected with the entrepreneurial concept developed in the E+ project, the main challenge is to identify business-academia opportunities of cooperation in research that can be leveraged by and to other members of Unite!. The purpose of the value proposition is reinforcing business-academia cooperation, through the identification of the needs and value for all actors.

State of the art

The literature review about best practices of business-academia cooperation suggested how the Unite! network can work for the **reduction of barriers** and the empowerment of facilitators for university-industry collaboration in several aspects.

The first is to **help reduce bureaucratic barriers to collaboration**. This can be achieved by establishing standardized collaboration models, protocols and contracts that take into account the experience of successful collaborations in the past. The second is to **increase the innovative mindset of researchers**, making them more sensitive to the role of industry in transforming their discoveries into benefits for the citizens. The Unite! network can help increase the visibility of each researcher investigation and find the right interlocutor in the industry.

The interconnection of the innovation ecosystems of each partner university will allow the contact of researchers with industries that would be difficult to access. The Unite! network may serve to increase the importance of the university's reputational facilitator within its local industry, but also to extend it to the other universities in the consortium.

Finally, Unite! could also serve to share best practices in the relationship between universities and society. This aspect should include formal activities, such as technology transfer, but also the promotion of non-formal relationships. The latter must include the way of maintaining good and continuous relations with the alumni who, as we have seen, are privileged facilitators of the university's relationship with society.

Additionally, the patent analysis of the Unite! universities provides important insights regarding both the technological specialization and complementarities between the Unite! members and how it compares with the technological specialization of their respective regions.

In general, the Unite! universities tend to be dominant players among regional HEIs (Higher Education Institutions) seeking patent protection, though in Catalunya (ES51) and Rhône-Alpes (FR71) other HEIs have a strong presence.

For the period 2001-2020, the analysis of patterns of technological specialization of the six universities at the International Patent Classification (IPC) 1-digit level (8 IPC sections, A to H), shows that they tend to be mostly specialized in **G: Physics** and in **H: Electricity**, and also, though to a much lesser extent, in **C: Chemistry, Metallurgy** and in **F: Mechanical Engineering**.

In general, all the six universities are not relatively specialized in the sectors in which their regions are strong. The analysis shows that a significant distance exists between the universities' specializations and the respective regional specializations: The same happens in relation to the technological specialization of the European Patent Organization (EPO) region overall.

Most of the Unite! members have a diversified technological specialization, the exceptions being ULISBOA and INP GRENOBLE, whose concentration in a few technological areas has been on the rise (ULISBOA more focused on C: Chemistry, Metallurgy and A: Human Necessities, and INP Grenoble on sections H: Electricity and G: Physics).

Unsurprisingly, the technological specialization of the regions shows more stability than the technological specialization of both the universities that belong to Unite! and all the HEI in their regions. The estimated measure of technological distance shows that the gap between the specialization of the Unite! universities and that of their regions, despite remaining quite high, has been narrowing. The fact that universities' specialization displays lower stability over time reflects a smaller critical mass. Specialization fluctuation tends to intensify as the universities interact with different partners, or eventually experience higher turnaround rates, with younger researchers substituting retiring colleagues.

A limitation of the analysis is that patent applications tend to be more concentrated in some technological fields than in others. The fact that there are restrictions to software patentability in the EPO may affect the possible inferences regarding topics such as "digitalisation", for example.

The survey data collected from the Technology Transfer Offices (TTOs) allowed the determination of the core value of existing TTO offerings: the advice on IP and contracts, support for university spin-offs and strategic alliance establishment with industry partners, are the top three main activities carried out by Unite! TTOs. Students' placement and alumni relationship management are the less expressive activities in this context. The type of organizational stakeholders is concentrated in university spin-offs, large mainly domestic enterprises, and other technology-intensive SMEs whereas information and communication and professional, scientific, and technical activities are the top two sectors reached out by Unite! TTOs.

Towards a Unite!2030 strategy: Value proposition to reinforce business-academia cooperation

The following topics to be included in the value proposition:

- Importance of having access to people and teams with distinctive knowledge and know-how that are valuable to the Unite! Stakeholders;
- Greater IP portfolio that could be "packaged" / "bundled";
- Increase visibility, transparency, and communication of areas of expertise to Unite! members and stakeholders;
- Importance of centrality of each university that belongs to Unite! in their respective national/regional settings, providing reciprocal access to the alliance partners and to their local stakeholders to that network;
- Role of Unite! on providing better conditions for high growth start-ups;
- Implement the "one stop shop" concept with advantages in terms of costs and time savings.

In the sequence of the discussion, the following drafting of the value proposals was put forward:

For companies: Unite! is a recently established pan-European alliance of universities which have excelled in research and teaching in their respective regional/national contexts. Unite! convenes now a unique research power of 20,000-plus researchers across Europe, carrying out research in a multiplicity of frontier and applied areas. Unite! universities have been actively engaged in partnerships with companies in the past and have the relevant know-how to keep up teaming with your company in finding innovative solutions. Since 2001 the members of Unite! submitted 743 patent applications to the European Patent Office, with its members managing an extensive patent portfolio, providing business opportunities across a diversified set of technological areas. Additionally, the network can make available talent through students' placement matching your needs.

For students: Unite! is a recently established pan-European alliance of universities which have excelled in research and teaching in their respective regional/national contexts. The members of the Unite! alliance have been actively engaged in partnerships with companies to develop innovative solutions. Unite! can now facilitate the mobility of its students to our partner companies across Europe.

Collaboration with Other Alliances (WP8)

State of the art

The seven partners of Unite!H2020 are also members of the **CLUSTER network** of which Unite! is a spin-off initiative. The two entities have continued collaborating through the creation of a specific working group within CLUSTER where the activities of the six European University alliances represented in CLUSTER exchange approaches and solutions and keep themselves up to date on current developments.

Unite! generally fosters a collaborative approach with other alliances acknowledging the fact that we aim for cooperation and not for competition and that the pool of alliances as a whole will only succeed if they move in the same direction and set compatible and complementary goals. Synergies have therefore been created with other alliances not represented in the CLUSTER network through the activities carried out by a specific task force generated by the Erasmus+ pilot project and through an outreach activity carried out by a specific working group (with a dedicated work package) under this Unite!H2020 pilot project.

Moreover, Unite! is committed to working together with the other alliances via the established **Forum of European Universities (FOR-EU)** to discuss and share intelligence resulting from:

1. The assessment of current practices, best practices and progress made/success stories implementing our long-term strategies
2. The identification of barriers – legal, financial and regulatory levels at which the barriers exists (Local, regional or European)

The Forum is an informal group, established to work together where it is of added value to:

1. Share information;
2. Benchmark the progress of our projects;
3. Collaborate on project activities and dissemination
4. Monitor the process of the initiative as a whole;
5. Join lobby efforts and coordinate lobby at the European and national level.

Actions at national and regional level promote the importance of the European Universities and present preliminary results of the alliance to the relevant decision-makers with the objective of receiving long-term support and possible extra financial resources to further empower the partners to scale-up their capacity and efforts to boost the full rollout of the alliance.

FOR-EU and the different subgroups of FOR-EU serve to exchange and comment on policy initiatives of the European Education and Research Areas. Among many policy statement and position papers Unite! contributed to through FOR-EU, Unite initiated together with Una Europa also a position paper on the European Degree that was also adopted by two other alliances.

Unite! as a brand is already well-known in the European Higher Education Area and even beyond and thrives to continue in leaving its mark with strong external visibility. Unite! on its own, as well as in cooperation with FOR-EU1, stronger bilateral or multilateral cooperation with alliances within FOR-EU1 will clearly show the strength of European Universities as role models for other higher education institutions. Notably, Unite! will, in the short-term and together with other European University alliances, additionally explore the possibility of offering the extended network of alliances to Ukrainian students and academics in exile. This joint ambition will be further discussed in FOR-EU.

Towards a Unite!2030 strategy for the collaboration of European Alliances

A benchmarking exercise was carried out within WP8 to identify alliances with similar and complementary visions and missions and a shortlist was produced. The initial discussion among Unite!

partners and the evaluation as well as benchmarking of other alliances, also based on the existing collaborative contacts to partners of other Alliances, led to the identification of **seven alliances for potential collaboration**: CIVICA, EuroTeQ, Una Europa, FORTHEM, EPICUR, Circle U and 4EU+.

Collaboration with other European University Alliances will be initiated in order to:

- Benchmark the progress of our projects and monitor the progress of the initiative as a whole;
- Join lobby efforts and coordinate lobby at the European and national level.
- assess current practices, best practices and progress made/success stories implementing our long-term strategies
- Identify barriers: legal, financial and regulatory levels at which the barriers exists (both regional and European)
- Promote the importance of the European Universities and present preliminary results of the alliance to the relevant decision-makers with the objective of receiving long-term support and possible extra financial resources to further empower the partners to scale-up their capacity and efforts to boost the full rollout of the alliance.
- Exchange and comment on policy initiatives of the “European Education and Research Areas”

UNITE.H2020 identified **two preferred pilot activities** with other European University Alliances: **two joint matchmaking workshops**, including an active participation of academic and administrative staff as well as Ph.D. students, to ensure a bottom-up involvement of the Alliances.

Unite! Action Plan

The UNITE.H2020 action plan defines a set of pilot actions and case studies built on the common R&I agenda for the implementation of the different transformation modules. These actions will be used as a test-bed for contributing to the R&I dimension of the Unite alliance in line with the common R&I objectives defined in the Challenges and Convergences Roadmap of WP2 (Deliverable 2.1) and with the shared, integrated, long-term joint strategy on education under development in Unite! E+. The R&I objectives and related pilots of UNITE.H2020 are reported in the following.

Research objective R1: Enhancement of multidisciplinary research

Pilot R1.1: Researchers open network in multidisciplinary areas (WP2)

An open network of Experts (researchers from partner university) will be fostered, taking benefit from the bottom-up network of energy faculty that is being established within the UNITE!E+ project and analysis of research groups done in WP6 (open science), and joining the efforts of WP3 (infrastructures) and WP5 (HR). The pilot will be agreed upon with the other WPs very likely the Energy area as planned in WP3. The digital requirements of this network will be also addressed. This open network can serve researchers to share materials, ideas and opportunities within a thematic open science community and build up collaboration for further research projects. This Researchers community will complement the effort ongoing in the energy field within the E+ WP8. The Experts will be involved in bottom-up co-creation of input for missions and societal challenges linked to SDGs within the 2021-2027 Horizon Europe programme and establish a dialogue with the Commission on successful cooperation models and future policy Initiatives.

Pilot R1.2: Sharing infrastructures for collaboration in Electrical energy (WP3)

This Pilot action is devoted to Electrical Energy, which covers many scientific and technological topics, in line with WP3 activities. The Pilot highlights are:

- Building a community of Infrastructures to share good practices
- Illustrating the guideline and emphasis on benefits/issues in sharing infrastructures
- Gathering research community in electrical engineering

Potential topics are in the following fields:

- HVDC networks for renewable energy integration
- Modern AC/DC hybrid networks
- Future renewable energy-dominated power systems
- Power electronics dominated power systems

The operating mode is given below:

- Identify doctoral students, masters and researchers that would benefit from this shared infrastructure across the alliance
- Identify infrastructures willing to be part of the pilot
- Matching both analysis.

Pilot R1.4: R&I Matchmaking Workshops 1 with Una Europa (+maybe Circle U) (WP8)

This matchmaking workshop will focus on matchmaking in research activities and, thus, supporting the following Research objectives, identified in the Unite! Challenges and Convergences Roadmap (Deliverable 2.1) for the Unite! common R&I Agenda:

- Objective R1: Enhancement of multidisciplinary research
- Objective R2: Promotion of a culture of excellence;
- Objective R3: Strengthening the impact of research on society;
- Objective R4: Open Science for knowledge co-creation.

This workshop is planned and addresses the topic “Sustainability and Sustainable Energy” from an interdisciplinary viewpoint. Along the guiding question “how to tackle sustainability from different points of view, namely Science & Technology and Social Sciences and Humanities?” Unite!, together with Una Europa, will organise a matchmaking and networking workshop that brings together at least 30 researchers from universities of both alliances.

The agenda of this workshop will include:

- Possible Horizon Calls addressing “sustainability” (Therefore a decent pre-screening of calls would be necessary)
- Key note speeches (e.g. from the Commission, DG RTD)
- Matchmaking / networking activities for collaborative proposals for external funding (incl. possible presentations of proposal ideas)
- Matchmaking / networking activities for potential PhD collaboration (might be in addition too much for a lunch-to-lunch meeting)

Pilot R1.5: R&I Matchmaking Workshops 2 (EuroTeQ tbd) (WP8)

A second workshop is planned as a matchmaking event that brings together two alliances with a similar focus, namely in Science and Technology. Apart from the above mentioned UNITE.H2020 objectives in research, this workshop is additionally addressing one of the innovation objectives identified in the Unite! Challenges and Convergences Roadmap (Deliverable 2.1), namely the objective I1, thus it includes:

- Objective R1: Enhancement of multidisciplinary research
- Objective R2: Promotion of a culture of excellence;
- Objective R3: Strengthening the impact of research on society;
- Objective R4: Open Science for knowledge co-creation.
- Objective I1: Enhancement of an entrepreneurial culture

The expected results of this workshop are ideas for initiating PhD collaboration, initiating joint research projects in common focus areas, to address open science and open access as well as entrepreneurship activities.

Research Objective R2: Promotion of a culture of excellence

Pilot R2.1: Strengthening R&I human capital with a Train of Trainers in Mentorship (WP5)

Based on the consultations made with early career researchers and research staff, one of the needs identified was associated with the mentorship programs for researchers and how to boost them, particularly a gap was found at the level of trainers. As consequence, it was decided to develop further actions that will support early career researchers to strengthen their careers. These are the training of trainers for the mentorship programs. This action is expected to cover three key aspects:

- The best examples of elements present in a mentoring program.
- How is the management of mentors by mentors and how can it be improved towards a common policy
- Best methodologies to train mentors in the universities.

The goal is to enable a joint vision and common policy for such kind of actions. This will be explored through the organization of a workshop

Pilot R2.2: Supporting R&I human capital with network of research support staff working on Marie Curie proposals (individual grants)

Researchers have considered that to enable their careers there is a need for training in preparing high impact proposals. Thus another pilot actions involves common training courses to Early Career Researchers : in fact, the strengths and gaps analysis evidenced that few partner universities offer training in transferable skills oriented to ECRs. To meet ECRs needs, the partners are willing to design and open already existing (online and English-speaking) training courses that can be offered to all ECRs of partner universities. This will allow to share the best practices and examples, contributing to strengthen ECRs skills, to open them to new mobility paths and to enable to raise funding to boost cooperations with the partners. For that, a joint workshop will shade light on the best examples from partners and a common action will be designed.

Research Objective R3: Research for society

Pilot R3.1: Unite! outreach activity: Unite! European Researchers' Night (WP7)

Connect unite! researchers and present research jointly. It is a true societal outreach event and, tailored to the target group, which are students and most important future students. We will use the interactive part after the researchers' presentations to include the students and focus on their questions, comments and input. We will also highlight and present unite! and the European University initiative by the EC and Secretary General, to foster visibility and access.

Target group: researchers and students/pupils

Pilot R3.1: Unite! outreach activity : unite! mapathon, coordinated mapping event (WP7)

Students are invited to lead an activity with small citizen groups (formed by volunteers, associations but public administrations as well) to map urbanistic needs in their local communities. The activities can integrate and respond to different perspectives when mapping the needs of the place, depending on the local community needs: gender inequalities, accessibility, mobility, open and green spaces, waste management system etc.

A mapathon is a tool to georeferenced points on a collaboratively map, and make them visible in real time. The organization of a collaborative unite! mapathon is an activity useful to foster social innovation with communities, groups of people or organizations who want to highlight e.g. a social problem through a map. The activity consists of a gathering information process that counts on the participation of the University community (mainly students), local public administrations and civil society organizations. The only requirement is that the participants must be equipped with GPS mobiles and Internet access.

It can be used at neighbourhood, school or campus level, for issues as diverse as identifying or denouncing accessibility problems, points of risk from a gender perspective, areas of waste accumulation or landscape problems, etc.. On the other hand, it can be used also in a positive way, highlighting resting points, biodiversity sites or safe spaces for example.

The information that is collected on the map is visible in real time.

The work could be linked with TF3 (Inclusion)

Target group: students, citizens and local public administrations

<https://mapathon.upc.edu/public/mapa>

Pilot R3.1: Unite! outreach activity: unite! creative challenge (WP7)

«HOPE» (INP-Grenoble) –Classes with different disciplines, creative challenge - <https://fondation-grenoble-inp.fr/nos-actions/chaire-hope/> dedicated to innovative solutions against energy precarity.

Activity axis: create knowledge through research, disseminate knowledge to drive action and create momentum. Simulate action by providing knowledge, connecting and animating networks. On this theme, we mobilize students from all over France and all sectors

Target group: students and researchers, local gov. and social service, business community and public policy makers, NGOs.

Research Objective R4: Open Science for knowledge co-creation

Pilot R4.1: Open Science comparative case study of Unite! research teams (WP6)

The objectives of Pilot R4.1 are:

- (1) to identify and mainstream best practices of open science and innovation of Unite! research teams;
- (2) to understand, identify, and demonstrate enablers and inhibitors of open science and innovation, and outline foundations for a new open science and innovation governance model and policy in Unite!
- (3) to explore how this model and policy contribute to the solving of gran societal challenges, and can be scalable-up at the European level.

This comparative case study of Unite! research team's best practices, enablers and inhibitors of open science and innovation is looking at differences across science disciplines in universities, in research cultures, and among young, intermediate, and consolidated scholars.

The aim is to interview 70 research teams' forerunners or active in either or both open science and open innovation activities, at Unite! Universities, that are promoting research and innovation for finding solutions for SDG2030.

The methodology for the study and for the data collection has been co-designed among partners. And the data collection is being performed through:

- semi-structured interviews of research team leaders, University leaders and science and innovation policymakers. The interview protocol was co-designed in WP6.
- informal interviews research team members (young, intermediate and consolidated scholars).
- observations of research team's open digital and physical research infrastructures.

Open science practices, principles and goals are ingrained in the development of Pilot R4.1. Therefore, a pilot set of quality data will be openly available in an open repository, in line with FAIR principles, to enhance open science for knowledge co-creation.

TT and Innovation Objective I1: Enhancement of an entrepreneurial culture

Pilot I1.1: Academia-business cooperation of Unite!: SEAT - decarbonizing the factory (WP4)

The pilot is still in the phase of being fully approved by SEAT

Collaboration SEAT-UPC and other companies in the ecosystem of Barcelona

Part of the zero carbon strategy of VW group: Electricity for plants in Europe and North and South America to be switched to renewables by 2030 (VW website)

Matches with WP4 strategy for analyzing a new model to bridge gap academia-business

Matches with the topics considered in H2020 proposal (SDGs, 7 Affordable and Clean Energy; 9 Industry Innovation and Infrastructure; 12 Responsible Consumption and Production)

Pilot I1.2: Academia-business cooperation of Unite! Merck Knowledge Graph (WP4)

Merck Knowledge Graph, it is a tool for promoting the culture of excellence, making knowledge available to all partners and enhancing multidisciplinary research and identifying common innovation potential (exploitation/transfer).

Collaboration Merck-TUDa and, potentially, more Unite! partners

The view is transversal, open to different topics, so it fits with H2020 proposal (digital transformation)

Matches with WP4 strategy for analyzing a new model to bridge gap academia-business

Pilot I1.3: Academia-business cooperation of Unite!: Merck Sustainability Hub (WP4)

Merck Sustainability Hub

Collaboration Merck-TUDa and other partners. Looks complicated to incorporate more Unite! partners, since the Hub is currently being set up.

Joint Research and Innovation as well as optimized Infrastructure for Start-ups (access to laboratories)

The view is transversal, open to different topics, so it fits with H2020 proposal (digital transformation, SDGs 17s)

Matches with WP4 strategy for analyzing a new model to bridge gap academia-business.

Pilot I1.4: Academia-business cooperation of Unite!: Tech4Planet (WP4)

Pilot highlights:

- Tech4Planet Technology Transfer Hub*: a joint collaboration project involving 3 Universities, 3 Incubators and a Technology Transfer Investment fund (owned by Cassa Depositi e Prestiti a major Italian Institutional Investor) Each Univ. working hand to hand with its own incubator to identify deep science entrepreneurial projects, performing first technical due diligence and supporting tech incubation during the POC phase. The investor support financially the POC, obtaining rights on future equity and rights on shares of licensing income. The Hub aggregates other Investment funds and corporates to sustain subsequent growth phases both financially and industrially. Active in SDG 17.
- Academia-business cooperation of Unite!: Tech4Planet (WP4) HP Chair on Innovation in Digital Manufacturing. Coordinated by UPC, with potential participation of the Essen ecosystem. Collaborating in the implementation of Digital Manufacturing and development of Industry 4.0. In planning stage. Active in SDG 9, 17.

TT and Innovation Objective I2: Digital transformation

Pilot I2.1: Infrastructures remote connection for data sharing: Smart Districts & Living Labs (WP3)

This pilot is dedicated to Smart Districts and Living Labs, in line with WP3 activities. The Pilot highlights are the following:

- Building a community of Infrastructures to share good practices
- Illustrating the guideline and emphasis on benefits/issues in sharing infrastructures
- Gathering research community in living labs, sharing datas

The operating mode is mentioned below:

- Identify doctoral students, masters and researchers that would benefit from shared infrastructure across the alliance
- Identify infrastructures willing to be part of the pilot
- Matching both analysis

Pilot I2.2: Academia-business cooperation of Unite!: Digital manufacturing (WP4)

Pilot highlights:

- HP Chair on Innovation in Digital Manufacturing in UPC (already in operation)
- Interest of Hessenmetall in Digital Manufacturing (shown to TUDa and during 4th Unite! Dialogue in Barcelona)
- Matches with WP4 strategy for analyzing a new model to bridge the gap academia-business
- Matches with the topics considered in H2020 proposal (SDGs, 7 Affordable and Clean Energy; 9 Industry Innovation and Infrastructure; 12 Responsible Consumption and Production)

R&I TRANSVERSAL Pilot

IRIS Network of Research & Innovation Services (WP2)

A joint Research&Innovation Service seems mandatory for the alliance implementation beyond the exchange of good practices. This will include the network of Grant Offices at each partners' university, the Technology Transfer Offices (to be set up in WP4) and the HR staff (that will develop WP5 initiatives). The pilot is aimed at establishing first of all a network of Grant Office, that will help targeting additional and complementary funding at national and EU level to implement the pilot and study cases of the action plan and will set a common line towards future support for the application to EU funding. Within the pilot regular interaction modalities among the above mentioned offices/staff services will be identified, in order to push forward the international collaboration opportunities, thus being a first seed of institutional transformation in the direction of the Alliance. The network is indeed meant to empower the 'UNITE European Universities' research and innovation transformation and become an interface with the EU for the design and deployment of future EU funding support. The assessment of the digital requirements of this network will be part of this pilot and of D2.3.